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Research article

Extracting reproductive parameters from GPS tracking data for a nesting raptor in Europe

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Understanding population dynamics requires estimation of demographic parameters like mortality and productivity. Because obtaining the necessary data for such parameters can be labour-intensive in the field, alternative approaches that estimate demographic parameters from existing data can be useful. High-resolution biologging data are frequently available for large-bodied bird species and can be used to estimate survival and productivity. We extend existing approaches and present a freely available tool ('NestTool') that uses GPS tracking data at hourly resolution to estimate important productivity parameters such as home range establishment, breeding initiation, and breeding success. NestTool first extracts 42 movement metrics such as time spent within a user-specified radius, number of revisits, home range size, and distances between most frequently used day and night locations from the raw tracking data for each individual breeding season. These variables are then used in three independent random forest models to predict whether individuals exhibited home range behaviour, initiated a nesting attempt, and successfully raised fledglings. We demonstrate the use of NestTool by training models with data from 258 individual red kites *Milvus milvus* from Switzerland tracked for up to 7 years, and then applied those models to tracking data from different red kite populations in Germany where detailed observations of nests and their outcomes existed for validation. The models achieved > 90% accurate classification of home range and nesting behaviour in validation data, but slightly lower (80–90%) accuracy in classifying the outcome of nesting attempts, because some individuals frequently returned to nests despite having failed. NestTool provides a graphical user interface that allows users to manually annotate individual seasons for which model predictions exceed a user-defined threshold of uncertainty. NestTool will facilitate the estimation of demographic parameters from tracking data to inform population assessments, and we encourage ornithologists to test NestTool for different species.

Keywords: Biologging, fecundity, machine learning, telemetry

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Introduction

Understanding the dynamics of animal populations requires data on key demographic processes such as mortality, productivity, and dispersal. The widespread adoption of miniaturized automated tracking devices has facilitated the study of seasonal migration patterns of many animal species in great detail (Kays et al. 2015, Panuccio et al. 2021). So far, however, relatively few studies have used these large-scale GPS tracking data to extract information on survival (Klaassen et al. 2014, Sergio et al. 2019, Swift et al. 2020, Buechley et al. 2021, Serratos et al. 2024) or reproduction (Picardi et al. 2020, Schreven et al. 2021, Bowgen et al. 2022, Overton et al. 2022, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022, Eisaguirre et al. 2023).

Reproductive performance in long-lived species generally improves with age, and the timing and outcome of the first reproduction can have major implications for population dynamics (Blas et al. 2009, Sergio et al. 2011, Weimerskirch 2018). As young birds recruit into the breeding population, their first breeding attempts often fail at an early stage and can therefore be difficult to detect through field observations (Péron et al. 2014, Kidd et al. 2015). Because the collection of reproductive information from individuals in the field can be very time- and labour-intensive, using tracking data to determine when the first reproduction occurs and how successful it is may therefore offer additional detail to help understand the population dynamics of long-lived species (Murgatroyd et al. 2023).

Information on reproduction can be derived from animal tracking data if individuals follow recurring patterns that can be reliably identified and distinguished. For example, the nest as a central location will be visited frequently during the breeding phase, resulting in typical central-place foraging movement patterns that can be detected in tracking data (van der Wal et al. 2015, Riotte-Lambert et al. 2016, Picardi et al. 2020, Bowgen et al. 2022, Overton et al. 2022, Eisaguirre et al. 2023). The identification of nesting behaviour can be further improved by using both GPS and accelerometry data, as periods of incubation lead to unique periodic patterns with near-zero movement (Schreven et al. 2021, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022). However, accelerometry data are not ubiquitously available, and models that reliably identify nesting and breeding success based solely on location data can be robust enough to compare reproductive parameters of different populations of the same species (Picardi et al. 2020, Eisaguirre et al. 2023).

While several methods have been described to extract nesting and breeding success information from bird tracking data (Table 1), only one of these methods was developed to predict the settlement process (e.g. the establishment of a home range; Whitfield et al. 2022), and several methods are computationally very intensive. We therefore extend existing approaches (Picardi et al. 2020, Schreven et al. 2021, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022) and provide a flexible and fast algorithm (hereafter referred to as 'NestTool') predicting important demographic parameters of birds using only GPS tracking data. NestTool adds to existing approaches (Table 1)

by not only estimating nest initiation and breeding success, but also the probability of home range establishment – an important process in the recruitment of young birds (Whitfield et al. 2022). NestTool also reduces the computational burden of predicting demographic parameters, which is useful because many tracking studies now routinely equip > 100 individuals, and data volumes are expected to increase in the coming decades (Kays et al. 2022). We demonstrate the application of NestTool for a common raptor species in Europe with large data volumes (<https://www.life-eurokite.eu/de/publikationen/red-kite-telemetry-project.html>).

The red kite *Milvus milvus* is a widespread European raptor species that has recently recovered from historic persecution in central Europe (Mammen et al. 2017, Aebischer and Scherler 2021), but is still vulnerable to anthropogenic causes of mortality in south-western Europe (Mateo-Tomás et al. 2020, Sergio et al. 2021). Despite being a long-lived species with delayed maturity, the temporal fluctuation of productivity was the most important demographic driver of the growth rate of red kite populations (Sergio et al. 2021, Pfeiffer and Schaub 2023). A better understanding of the age at which young red kites recruit into the breeding population and contribute to the reproductive output of a population is therefore a key demographic parameter that is so far poorly studied (Katzenberger et al. 2021, Literák et al. 2022, Pfeiffer and Schaub 2023). A tool that allows an objective assessment of this recruitment process would therefore be a useful advance for studying red kite population dynamics.

Besides population dynamics, the movements of red kites have attracted much research interest and > 2000 individuals have been equipped with tracking devices in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Spain, and France (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Mattsson et al. 2022, Pfeiffer and Meyburg 2022). These tracking efforts have revealed information on mortality and survival (Sergio et al. 2019, Katzenberger et al. 2021, Mattsson et al. 2022), migration and dispersal (Maciorowski et al. 2019, García-Macía et al. 2022a, Literák et al. 2022, Scherler et al. 2023b), and revealed that successfully breeding red kites showed smaller home ranges than unsuccessfully breeding birds (Spatz et al. 2022). Therefore, telemetry data obtained from individuals during the breeding season may be sufficient to extract information on breeding initiation and success. However, the ranging behaviour of red kites varies markedly between countries and years, with home range sizes dependent on landscape composition, habitat structure, age, sex, and food availability (Pfeiffer and Meyburg 2015, Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Spatz et al. 2022). There is an urgent need to compare the demographic performance of different populations using standardised approaches (Mattsson et al. 2022), and using tracking data to extract demographic parameters can increase comparability across populations (Murgatroyd et al. 2023).

Here we describe the structure and functionality of NestTool, and present an example application where we tested this tool using data from 697 breeding seasons of individually tracked red kites in Switzerland where the outcome was known from field observations. We further validated the

Table 1. Overview of existing methods to extract home range, nest initiation, and breeding success estimates from bird telemetry data.

Tool	NestTool	'nestR'	Hierarchical model	AWS machine	Threshold decisions	Threshold decisions	AFTS algorithm	Curve-fitting
citation	this study	Picardi et al. 2020, Mov. Ecol. 8: 24	Eisaguirre et al. 2023, Methods Ecol. Evol. 14: 2110–2122	Overton et al. 2022, Mov. Ecol. 10: 23	Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022, Anim. Biotelemetry 10: 24	Schreven et al. 2021, Anim. Biotelemetry 9: 1	Whitfield et al. 2022, Front. Ecol. Evol. 10	Bowgen et al. 2022, Ecol. Evol. 12: e9509
species tested on	altricial (red kite)	altricial (wood stork, lesser kestrel, Mediterranean gull)	altricial (golden eagle)	precocial (mallard, gadwall, pintail, teal, wigeon)	precocial (Greenland white-fronted goose)	precocial (pink-footed goose)	altricial (golden eagle)	precocial (curlew)
sex used for building tool	M+F	M+F	M+F	F	F	F	M+F	M
sex that incubates clutch	F	M+F	F	F	F	F	not applicable	M+F
sample size on which tool was tested	659	233	85	131	64	13	25	26
GPS temporal data resolution tested	1 h	1 h	2 h	1 h	15 min	10 min	> 12 h	15 min
accuracy of predictions	0.81–1.0	0.87–1.0	0.83–1.0	0.82–0.95	0.95–1.0	0.87–0.99	0.8–1.0	not specified
nest detection procedure	random forest	classification and regression tree	hierarchical movement model	ensemble of machine learning models	decision tree	recursive partitioning/ regression tree	rule-based use of minimum convex polygons	manual curve inspection
nest failure assessment procedure	algorithmic prediction	hierarchical survival model	hierarchical survival model	inferred from algorithmic prediction	threshold	threshold	none	visual
movement variables used for classification	42	3	2	68	2	2	5	2
model easily visualised	no	yes	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
predicts existence of home range	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	no
predicts existence of nesting attempt	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes
returns location of potential nest site	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes
predicts outcome of nesting attempt	yes	yes	yes	(yes)	yes	yes	no	yes

(Continued)

Table 1. Continued.

Tool	NestTool	'nestR'	Hierarchical model	AWS machine	Threshold decisions	Threshold decisions	AFTS algorithm	Curve-fitting
predicts timing of nest failure	no	yes	yes	yes	(yes)	no	no	(yes)
visualisation of nest locations and movement metrics	yes	(yes)	no	no	no	no	(no)	no
facilitates manual annotation based on visualisation	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
highlights uncertain classification	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no
transferability (R-package or code available)	<u>NestTool</u>	<u>'nestR'</u>	<u>code</u>	<u>code</u>	<u>code</u>	not available	<u>code</u>	not available
programming knowledge required	medium	medium	high	very high	low	low	low	low
computation time	short	intermediate	long	long	short	short	short	long (manual)
financial cost	free	free	free	AWS server fee	free	free	free	free
knowledge of phenology needed	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
minimum duration of nesting attempt that can be detected (days)	not specified	7–14	not specified	1	< 3	3	<i>not applicable</i>	3–9

utility of the algorithm by applying it to data from two separate red kite populations in Germany where the outcome was also known from field observations. We provide guidance on what movement patterns indicate successful breeding and provide software to rapidly annotate existing tracking data with information about breeding initiation and success. We examine the conditions under which an accurate prediction of nest outcome is not possible, and caution researchers that typical tracking data may not be able to classify all breeding episodes correctly. NestTool facilitates the rapid estimation of home range establishment, breeding initiation and success, and will therefore contribute to a better understanding of important demographic processes that drive population dynamics of red kites (Pfeiffer and Schaub 2023) and other species.

Methods

Overview of the approach

Previous approaches to predict the nesting behaviour of birds based on tracking data used either simple decision trees and thresholds (Picardi et al. 2020, Schreven et al. 2021, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022), hierarchical models describing the movement process (Eisaguirre et al. 2023), or advanced artificial intelligence algorithms for daily status prediction (Table 1; Overton et al. 2022). We opted for a user-friendly approach that employs easily accessible machine learning algorithms (Pichler and Hartig 2023) to predict the occurrence of hierarchically nested breeding behaviour at a seasonal timescale, without attempting to predict the breeding status at shorter timescales (Picardi et al. 2020, Overton et al. 2022, Eisaguirre et al. 2023). In particular, we aimed to predict whether territorial ranging behaviour occurs (e.g. whether the bird occupies a ‘home range’, defined as a consistent area over which an individual regularly travels during the breeding season in search for food (Powell and Mitchell 2012)), whether a nesting attempt is made, and whether the nesting attempt was successful (defined as producing at least one fledgling) based on GPS tracking data (Table 1). Red kites can obtain a home range in breeding areas at the age of 2–3 years and typically start breeding at the age of 3–7 years (Newton et al. 1989, Evans et al. 1998, Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Scherler et al. 2023a). Their behaviour during the breeding period differs between sexes, with males generally provisioning incubating females and therefore moving around more during the incubation period (García-Macía et al. 2022b). Our approach therefore takes the age and sex of tracked red kites into account when deriving information on the reproductive status from tracking data (these data are described in more detail in ‘Estimating reproductive parameters with red kite tracking data from Switzerland’).

We developed ‘NestTool’ – a tool that first identifies a potential nest site as the GPS location with the greatest amount of time spent and the greatest number of revisits by the focal individual within a user-specified radius (e.g. 50

m) and time period (breeding season adjusted for local phenology). The radius and period can be specified by the user to ensure that NestTool can be adjusted to different populations or species and their respective movement behaviour and phenology. The radius will be applied to every GPS location within the specified period. The plausible nest location is then used to calculate distances to all other GPS locations and to summarize median daily distances from the nest, the number of revisits to the nest radius (after temporary absence from that radius), the amount of time spent within the nest radius, and the amount of time spent outside another user-defined radius indicative of a typical home range (e.g. 2 km; Hötter et al. 2017, Scherler et al. 2023a). This radius is only applied to the plausible nest location and should be chosen based on the typical foraging movements of a breeding bird, and accommodate typical foraging distances even if these trips do not occur in all directions from the nest. We repeat this procedure for all nocturnal (between sunset and sunrise) and all diurnal locations and calculate the distance between the locations where most of the daytime and most of the nighttime is spent, based on the premise that nesting birds will likely roost on or very near their nest site, whereas non-nesting birds can often roost farther away from any diurnal congregation sites (Heiniger 2020, Aebischer and Scherler 2021). We further calculate the home range area as the 95% and 99% minimum convex polygon and extract the last day of the breeding season when the plausible nest location identified above was visited to within the user-specified nest radius. All movement metrics are calculated for distinct periods of the breeding season. These variables are then combined with information on individuals (age and sex) in three independent models that are fitted sequentially. NestTool is available as an R package (www.r-project.org) on GitHub: <https://github.com/Vogelwarte/NestTool>.

Model description and specification

Each of NestTool’s three models aims to predict a binary outcome (occurrence of home range, nest, and success – yes or no) using a random forest algorithm, which is a powerful machine-learning algorithm that can extract useful information from many predictor variables (Breiman 2001, Prasad et al. 2006, Cutler et al. 2007, Pichler and Hartig 2023). Because of the large number of potential movement metrics that may distinguish between home range and nesting behaviours and breeding success, and the fact that many of these variables may be correlated or interact, a random forest is a suitable algorithm that has been used to distinguish other movement behaviours (Thiebault et al. 2018, Carneiro et al. 2022). A random forest is based on the aggregation of hundreds of individual classification trees, the basic unit used to infer behavioural patterns in previously published approaches (Shamoun-Baranes et al. 2012, Picardi et al. 2020). Each classification tree uses a random subset of training data which will therefore vary among the different trees, facilitating cross-validation of the predictive performance. A random forest is conceptually similar to the stochastic gradient boosting

employed by approaches predicting daily behavioural states (Overton et al. 2022).

Like other machine learning models, random forests can be tuned to improve predictive accuracy by adjusting parameters that control how the model distinguishes between outcomes. Because the ideal value of these parameters to achieve the most accurate prediction may vary depending on the composition of the training data set, our tool iterates over two important parameters, namely the number of individual classification trees (from 500 to 5000) and the number of different variables tried at each node (from 1 to 15). For each combination of parameters, a random forest model is fitted using the R package 'ranger' (www.r-project.org, Wright and Ziegler 2017), and the prediction error of internally cross-validated (out-of-bag) test data is extracted from each fitted model. The parameters resulting in the lowest prediction error are then used to fit the main model and extract the most important predictor variables using a permutation procedure (Strobl et al. 2007, Grömping 2009, Janitza et al. 2013). The available data are randomly divided, and a fraction of the data is used to train the main model, while the remainder of the data are retained to test the accuracy of predictions of this model. NestTool allows users to specify what fraction of their data should be used for model training and testing. We used a fraction of 70% for model training and report the accuracy of predictions referring to the training and test data separately, with accuracy defined as the proportion of correctly classified cases. A 'correct' classification is defined as a case where the predicted outcome of a reproductive event (i.e. the existence of a home range, a nesting attempt, or the nesting success) in an individual season matches the observed outcome of the same event.

Description of the workflow of analysis

The analysis requires two input files which contain the raw tracking data and life history information per individual and season, respectively. We first extract movement metrics (Supporting information) for each individual and season, which are calculated based on various user-specified input values to curtail the data to the spatial and temporal domain of interest, and to specify different phases of the breeding season that allow for the characterisation of movement behaviour of breeding birds to change between incubation and chick rearing. The input values (the dates when changes in breeding behaviour are expected for the target population) are therefore deliberately required to accommodate differences among populations and species, and should be specified based on the focal populations' typical breeding phenology (if there is very large variation in the timing of breeding, we recommend performing the analysis separately for data subsets with more homogenous phenology).

Similarly, the spatial scale over which recursions to a nest location and presence and absence times will be evaluated must be specified by the user, based on the general movement characteristics of the species of interest. These parameters therefore allow different scales for different species or

populations (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Spatz et al. 2022), and for differences in the general average locational precision of the tracking data. However, the absolute value of the movement metrics is not important for the predictive accuracy of the model, because only the difference between birds that are nesting (successfully) and those that are not nesting (or not successfully) is important for the tool to work accurately.

For each individual season a total of 42 movement metrics that reflect home range areas, distances, residence times, and revisitation patterns of the respective individual over the user-specified phases and radii of the breeding season are calculated (Supporting information; see package documentation for guidance on how to specify the radii and temporal phases). By calculating movement metrics for certain breeding phases, temporal changes in movement behaviour that occur throughout the breeding season can be captured and used to inform the model (Schreven et al. 2021, Overton et al. 2022, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022). Residence times and revisitation patterns are calculated with the function 'getRecursions' in the R package 'recurse' (www.r-project.org, Bracis et al. 2018).

Once the movement metrics have been calculated, there are three sequential steps to identify and predict breeding behaviours, namely 1) whether individuals have a home range (defined as a consistent area over which an individual regularly travels during the breeding season in search of food), which is typically shown by frequent returns to and long residency times at a single location (estimated as the 'plausible nest location'); 2) whether birds initiate a nesting attempt, which results in similar movements to having a home range, but with even more stringent attachment to a single location (the 'plausible nest location') and very short distances between the locations most used during day and night; and 3) whether the nesting attempt was actually successful (defined as at least one live fledgling leaving the nest), which results in frequent returns to the nest throughout the entire breeding season and regular presence for long periods of time, especially during the early chick-rearing period. NestTool provides two functions for each of those steps: one to train a model that requires data where the actual behaviour of the tracked birds was observed in the field and is therefore validated (e.g. through field observations during which a tagged individual was observed on a nest and the outcome of the nesting attempt could be confirmed by repeated observations confirming whether fledglings left the nest or not (Scherler et al. 2023a)), and a second function to use that model to predict the behaviour for tracked birds (which can include birds for which the actual behaviour was not validated through field observations). If no training data with validated behaviours exist for a population, the models contained in the tool can be used to predict breeding behaviours for any data set that meets the minimum data requirements (specified by the user, in our case 800 GPS locations per individual over the breeding season) – but we caution that these predictions rely explicitly on the assumption that the patterns observed in red kites from Switzerland are transferrable to the population of interest.

The steps above can classify home range establishment, breeding initiation and success based on movement metrics, but there will always be individual movement behaviours that have very high uncertainty in classification. NestTool, therefore, provides not only the functions above to predict probabilities of each reproductive behaviour, but also a graphical user interface (based on R 'shiny'; [Chang et al. 2023](#)) to visually inspect an individual's movements over a season to manually determine behaviours when the predicted probabilities exceed a user-specified threshold of 'uncertainty'. Users can specify the 'uncertainty' they are willing to accept, which is the threshold of the probability of assignment (e.g. if a user specifies an 'uncertainty' of 25%, then all seasons with predicted probabilities < 0.25 and > 0.75 are accepted and only those with predicted probabilities in the range 0.25–0.75 are presented for manual inspection). To aid in this manual annotation, the user is presented with a map of the tracking data locations, and graphs that show the development of five movement metrics over time (Supporting information). These movement metrics are calculated over moving 5 day windows with an overlap of 2 days, where the median or maximum of a given metric is summarised over each 5 day window to smoothen out daily variation in movements that could be influenced by weather and obscure longer-term patterns ([Bowgen et al. 2022](#), [Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022](#)). The manual annotation of breeding initiation and success (or the acknowledgement by the user that outcomes are too uncertain to classify) is then saved and can be combined with the automated classification to extract important demographic parameters for the tracked population solely from the tracking data.

Estimating reproductive parameters with red kite tracking data from Switzerland

We tracked 324 red kites (see the Supporting information for age and sex distribution) since 2013 using harness-attached solar-powered GPS tags of different manufacturers ([Aebischer and Scherler 2021](#), [Orgeret et al. 2023](#), [Scherler et al. 2023b](#)) that have been shown to cause no adverse effects on survival, recruitment, and breeding performance of birds from 0 to 28 years of age ([Peniche et al. 2011](#), [Sergio et al. 2015](#), [Longarini et al. 2023](#)). During the same period, red kites were intensively monitored by field observers and all home ranges, breeding attempts, and nest outcomes (number of fledged young) of all tracked birds were visually assessed. Field observers on the ground repeatedly checked all home ranges and nests with binoculars (roughly once or twice a month per bird), nest cameras, and tree climbers throughout the breeding season ([Scherler et al. 2023a](#)), so that the breeding behaviour and success for all tracked birds was known from independent field observations.

We first extracted data for the core breeding season of red kites in Switzerland and discarded all tracking locations south of 45°N and west of 4°E, and before 11 March and after 24 June, which are the earliest egg-laying and earliest fledging dates in our study population ([Aebischer and Scherler 2021](#),

[Scherler et al. 2023a](#)). Although the exact brood initiation and fledging times of those nests were known, these dates were not used to build models because the ultimate goal of the model is to predict the outcome of reproductive events for which such data do not exist. We therefore chose to curtail the season to the earliest fledging date to avoid movement patterns after fledging being mistaken for similar movement patterns occurring after nest failure. We then resampled all tracking data from a higher resolution (1–60 min) to a 1 hourly interval, matching the temporal data resolution that is generally available for most data sets in Europe ([Maciorowski et al. 2019](#), [García-Macía et al. 2022b](#), [Literák et al. 2022](#)). Because the identification of reproductive behaviour requires regular data throughout the breeding season, we discarded all individual seasons ($n = 336$; 33%) that did not provide at least 800 locations in the time period specified above (roughly eight locations per day for our 105 day season, but note that only the total number of locations is specified and evaluated and not the actual or average number of locations per day).

For each individual and season, we used the functions described above to extract all the explanatory variables from the filtered tracking data. We used a 50 m radius around the most frequently visited day and night locations to identify potential nests, and a 2000 m radius to quantify the time spent outside the typical home range, because these distances encompass the typical size of home ranges in our study population ([Scherler et al. 2023a](#)). We separated the breeding season of red kites in Switzerland into five distinct phases during which different movement behaviours could be expected: the settlement phase when birds typically arrive in their home range and prepare for nesting (11 March – 15 April, but note that in exceptional cases some birds may already lay eggs in this phase), the first incubation phase (15–30 April), the second incubation phase (30 April – 15 May), the first (15–30 May), and second (1–24 June) chick rearing phases ([Aebischer and Scherler 2021](#), [Spatz et al. 2022](#)). The phase when we expected very frequent returns to the nest during the presence of small chicks was specified from 1 May to 1 June ([Scherler et al. 2023a](#)), which overlaps with the typical late incubation and early chick rearing phases. Note that these dates are approximate and will not accurately capture the exact breeding phase for every individual season, but these approximate dates still provide the random forest algorithm with some flexibility to accommodate individual variation in nesting phenology ([Scherler et al. 2023a](#)). To provide a comparison of the computational time required by these analyses we used the exact same input data and input parameters in the R package 'nestR' (www.r-project.org, [Picardi et al. 2020](#)) and report the computation time of data processed in NestTool and in 'nestR' on the same machine (Intel Core i7-1255U 1.70 GHz processor and 40 GB random-access memory).

Testing the tool with red kite tracking data from Germany

To test whether the models developed for red kites in Switzerland could accurately predict the reproductive

behaviour of individuals of different populations in Germany, we used data from 163 individual seasons of 65 individual birds (see the Supporting information for age and sex distribution) tracked between 2010 and 2023 in eastern Germany (Pfeiffer and Meyburg 2015, 2022, Nicolai et al. 2017). The reproductive behaviour and nesting success of these birds was independently determined through detailed field observations (Pfeiffer 2009, Kolbe and Nicolai 2017, Grüneberg and Karthäuser 2019). We discarded all tracking locations south of 50°N and west of 9°E, and adjusted the temporal definitions of the breeding season to the local phenology as follows: start of season 15 March, start of incubation 5 April, start of hatching 15 May, end of brooding period 15 June, first fledging 10 July. Because home ranges of red kites in Germany are more than twice as large as in Switzerland (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Spatz et al. 2022), we also adjusted the definitions of the 'nest radius' to 150 m and of the 'home range radius' to 5000 m (Kolbe and Nicolai 2017). We extracted all movement metrics based on those spatial and temporal definitions, and predicted reproductive behaviour for red kites in Germany using the models trained with data from red kites in Switzerland.

Results

Model development with data from Switzerland

We used NestTool to train random forest models with red kite tracking data from Switzerland that encompassed 697 individual seasons from a total of 258 tracked individuals that met the minimum criteria of 800 locations during a breeding season. Some individuals were tracked over several years (range 1–7). The presence ($n = 360$) or absence ($n = 337$) of a home range and a nesting attempt (yes = 296, no = 401) were known for all individual seasons, and the outcome of a nesting attempt was known for 257 individual seasons, of which 177 successfully raised at least one fledgling, while 80 nesting attempts failed.

The model to classify the presence of a home range classified 99.5% of individual seasons correctly in the cross-validated test data (Table 2, Supporting information). The most influential variables in predicting the existence of a home range were the total amount of time spent within the radius of a potential nest (residence_time_day, tottime_nest),

the number of revisits to a potential nest site during the day (revisits_day), and the median distance between daytime and the most frequently used nighttime locations (median_day_dist_to_max_night; Supporting information).

The model classifying the presence of a nesting attempt classified 95.2% of individual seasons correctly in the cross-validated test data (Table 2, Supporting information), while 7.0% of individual seasons could not be classified with the user-specified uncertainty of < 25% or > 75% probability (Fig. 1). The most influential variables in predicting a nesting attempt were again the total amount of time spent within a potential nest radius (tottime_nest, residence_time_night), and the number of revisits to a potential nest site during the day (revisits_day; Supporting information). The process to prepare the data, train the model, and predict the existence of nesting attempts for 697 individual seasons took 12 minutes in NestTool, while processing the same data for the same purpose took 44 minutes in 'nestR' and classified 91.8% individual seasons correctly (Table 2).

The model to classify the outcome of a nesting attempt was applied to those seasons that had been classified to have a nesting attempt in the previous step, and correctly classified 80.5% of those individual seasons in the cross-validated test data (Table 2, Supporting information). In total, 69.6% of seasons could be classified with a high (> 75% or < 25%) probability of assignment, and the accuracy among those was 96.7%, while the remaining 30.4% of all seasons could not be classified with high certainty (assignment probability > 25% and < 75%) and were therefore flagged up for manual annotation (Fig. 2). The most influential variable in predicting breeding success was the number of revisits to the nest site during the second chick phase (revisitsChick2; Supporting information). The process to train the model and predict the outcome of nesting attempts for 257 individual seasons took 27 seconds in NestTool, while estimating nest survival for the same data took 130 minutes in 'nestR' and correctly classified 77.6% of individual seasons (Table 2).

The overall breeding propensity of the tracked red kite population in our study area in Switzerland was 83.1% when inferred from tracking data (compared to 82.2% observed), and overall breeding success (the proportion of birds that initiated a nesting attempt and successfully raised fledglings) inferred from the tracking data was 74.5% (compared to 68.8% observed). Based on the predicted occurrence of home range behaviour, we estimated that 0% of 2 year old

Table 2. Proportion of correctly classified reproductive parameters from GPS tracking data of red kites in Germany and Switzerland using the newly developed NestTool and the existing package 'nestR' (Picardi et al. 2020) for comparison. Data subset indicates whether the data were used for model fitting ('training') or not ('validation'). n indicates the number of individual breeding seasons that were classified, but note that the number for breeding success was lower because not all individuals initiated a nesting attempt. See the Supporting information for all confusion matrices.

Country	Data subset	Method	n	home range	breeding initiation	breeding success
Switzerland	training	NestTool	488	0.990	0.988	0.967
	internal validation	'nestR'	697		0.918	0.776
Germany	external validation	NestTool	209	0.995	0.952	0.805
		'nestR'	99	0.960	0.848	0.847
			99		0.899	0.696

Figure 1. Example plots of the temporal sequence of two movement metrics (home range size as 95% minimum convex polygon, and median daily travel distance, both calculated over 5-day windows with a 2-day overlap between adjacent windows) for three adult female red kite individuals that initiated a breeding attempt (left), did not breed (centre), and exhibited behaviour that resulted in uncertain (assignment probability > 25% and < 75%) classification (right).

Figure 2. Example plots of the temporal sequence of three movement metrics (median daily time spent at the nest, median of the daily maximum distance from the nest, and maximum length of time consecutively away from nest, all calculated over 5-day windows with a 2-day overlap between adjacent windows) for three adult female red kite individuals that failed in their nesting attempt (left), bred successfully (centre), and exhibited behaviour that resulted in an uncertain classification with an assignment probability > 25% and < 75% (right).

and 15.9% of 3 year old birds had established a home range (observed 17.2% of 3 year-olds), and that 0% of 2 year old birds and 7.6% of 3 year old birds initiated a nesting attempt (observed 8.3% of 3 year-olds).

Transferring the models to populations in Germany

We tested our models with red kite tracking data from Germany that encompassed 163 individual seasons from a total of 65 tracked individuals, some of which were tracked over several years (range 1–7). After down-sampling the data from heterogeneous schedules ranging from 5 to 45 min resolution to 60 min intervals, and filtering the data to the seasonal phenology in Germany, we were able to predict reproductive parameters for 99 individual seasons from 63 individuals that met the criteria of at least 800 locations per season. These 99 individual seasons contained 98 seasons with home range, 89 nesting attempts, and 55 successful broods that were all observed and confirmed with field observations. The process to prepare the movement metrics required by the random forest model with our *data_prep* function, and predict the two responses of home range and breeding initiation took 2 minutes in NestTool, while the same process took 13 minutes with the same data on the same machine when using the package 'nestR'.

The home range model classified 94 seasons to have home range behaviour – an accuracy of 96.0% (Table 2). The single season without a home range was correctly classified, but had a higher predicted probability than three other seasons with home range behaviour that were erroneously classified. Compared to the 89 individual seasons that initiated a nesting attempt, our nesting model classified 78 seasons to breed – an accuracy of 84.8% (Table 2). Out of the 10 individual seasons without an observed nesting attempt, four seasons were erroneously classified to have a nesting probability of > 0.5 (false positive). Conversely, of the 89 actually observed nesting attempts 11 had a predicted nesting probability of < 0.5 (false negative), and were therefore missed (Supporting information). When we classified only those 59 individual seasons (59.9%) for which predictions were made with high certainty (assignment probability < 25% or > 75%), the overall accuracy increased to 89.8%.

The classification of breeding success for the data from Germany was as accurate as the classification of nesting attempts: out of the 55 individual seasons that raised at least one fledgling, our breeding success model classified 46 (83.6%) as successful, but erroneously classified 13.9% of failed nests as successful, leading to an overall accuracy of 84.7% (Table 2, Supporting information). For 61.8% of nesting attempts the outcome could not be classified with high certainty (assignment probability > 25% and < 75%) and would have required manual annotation; omitting these cases with low certainty increased the accuracy to 91.2%. The process to classify breeding success took 2 seconds in NestTool, while the same process took 31 minutes for the same data on the same machine when using the package 'nestR' and correctly classified the outcome of 77.6% of nesting attempts (Table 2).

Discussion

We present a tool that allows users to classify reproductive behaviour from GPS tracking data, and thus extract important reproductive parameters that can inform population dynamics (Katzenberger et al. 2021, Sergio et al. 2021, Pfeiffer and Schaub 2023). We developed these models with a large tracking data set of red kites in Switzerland, but show that they can be transferred to different populations in Germany and successfully classify reproductive behaviour. We encourage the use of NestTool to estimate demographic parameters and assess the broader transferability of this tool to other species and populations.

Although the movement patterns of birds repeatedly visiting a nest site to incubate eggs or feed chicks can be highly diagnostic and allow an accurate identification of a bird's breeding status (Picardi et al. 2020, Schreven et al. 2021, Bowgen et al. 2022, Overton et al. 2022, Ozsanlav-Harris et al. 2022, Eisaguirre et al. 2023), there are limitations to algorithmic identification (van der Wal et al. 2015). Red kites, in particular, can have individually variable home range behaviour, and also display profound differences in movements both between males and females and in different landscapes (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, García-Macía et al. 2022b, Spatz et al. 2022). Our tool provides probabilistic classifications of the occurrence of home ranging behaviour, breeding attempts, and breeding success, and facilitates easy manual inspection of cases that exceed a user's tolerance level of uncertainty. As with many other tools (Table 1), this tool is therefore not designed to work as a 'black box', but rather to assist researchers in the otherwise time-consuming manual inspection of events during the breeding season of tracked animals. By specifying the level of uncertainty that is tolerable, the user retains full control over the tradeoff between accepting automated predictions and manually annotating the reproductive behaviour of many individuals.

NestTool provided accurate predictions for red kites using the movement metrics that we chose, but we would welcome further evaluations of other species and suggestions for the improvement of this tool. We selected 42 variables (Supporting information) that are primarily focused on durations, distances, and home range areas. However, many alternative formulations are conceivable, including for example environmental features and historical context to put the movements of an individual into perspective of previous movements (Williams et al. 2020, Overton et al. 2022), or behavioural segmentation algorithms that would permit the automated detection of seasonal events and thus relax the stringent user-defined time points of major seasonal changes and allow individual flexibility in phenology. The extraction of environmental features from remote-sensing data may be highly beneficial for some species, but may not be available in many areas, may increase the computational cost of the tool, and make the transferability of models to other populations more problematic (Hothorn et al. 2011, Yates et al. 2018).

Because we did not use environmental or landscape variables, the variables that explained most of the variation

between birds with and without a home range mostly described the amount of time individuals spent in a certain radius around the centre of the home range, either during the day, at night, or in total (Supporting information). Territorial birds are expected to spend most of their time within their home range to be able to defend it against intruders and raise their brood (Hinde 1956, Kaufmann 1983), and the importance of time as a suitable predictor is therefore not surprising (Fauchald and Tveraa 2003, Barraquand and Benhamou 2008, Bracis et al. 2018). Similarly, the prediction of nesting behaviour relied primarily on the amount of time spent in the vicinity of a potential nest site, and the median distance between diurnal locations and where birds roosted at night (Supporting information), as most nesting birds generally sleep either on (females) or very close to (males) the nest (Aebischer and Scherler 2021). Surprisingly, sex was not a very important variable despite the two different roles that red kites play during incubation, with females incubating the eggs and males providing food for the female. We speculate that despite those two separate roles, the basic patterns of long attendance times and frequent returns to the specified nest radius of 50 m are similar, and the individual variability among red kites is large enough to obscure sex-related patterns of movement.

By contrast, the prediction of breeding success relied primarily on movement metrics during chick stages (Supporting information), including how often individuals revisited the nest during that phase, how much time they spent at the nest during the later chick stages, and when they last visited the nest site. Successful breeding requires chicks to be fed for 46 days, thus requiring multiple daily revisits to the nest for the entire duration of the breeding season, and regular presence at the nest until the chicks fledge (Aebischer and Scherler 2021, Scherler et al. 2023a). Although even unsuccessful breeders frequently remain in their home range and at their nest site, the number of revisits to the nest decreases when there are no more chicks that need to be fed (Scherler et al. 2023a). Moreover, in red kites nesting failure primarily occurs during incubation (Nägeli et al. 2022), which then leads to a distinctive relaxation of the repetitive visits to the nest and an increase in the distance from the nest already during incubation (Fig. 2). These revisitation patterns are broadly similar to what has been used to predict breeding success in other altricial raptor species (Picardi et al. 2020, Eisaguirre et al. 2023, Murgatroyd et al. 2023), and we are therefore optimistic that this tool could be adapted to identify reproductive behaviour for other species as well. The different roles that males and females play during reproduction may however require careful consideration: while in red kites only females incubate the eggs, both partners attend the nest and feed the chicks, and therefore engage in diagnostic behaviour around the nest site. A more equal division of labour would be beneficial and facilitate nest detection from both male and female tracking data (Picardi et al. 2020, Bowgen et al. 2022, Eisaguirre et al. 2023), whereas in species where only one sex assumes most or all of the incubation and chick rearing duties, models will need to be calibrated with data from that sex alone.

Using an automated tool to classify and predict the existence and outcome of reproductive behaviour has clear benefits when comparing several populations of a species. One key advantage of using tracking data at a temporal and spatial resolution that is available across a range of studies is the reduced influence of survey effort, which can affect the assessment of reproductive success based on field observations (Harris et al. 2020, Eisaguirre et al. 2023, Murgatroyd et al. 2023). By using a consistent algorithm across many populations, effects of survey effort or other regional adaptations in how reproductive parameters are measured in the field can be overcome when understanding the range-wide population dynamics of species (Mattsson et al. 2022). This is particularly important for demographic parameters that are difficult to estimate from field observations, such as whether reproduction occurs or not. Especially in long-lived species, and populations approaching the carrying capacity of the environment, an increasing proportion of adult birds may defer breeding or fail at early stages of the nesting cycle, which would be very difficult to detect using field surveys (López-Sepulcre and Kokko 2005, Catlin et al. 2019). Our tool offers a consistent classification approach that is independent of field survey effort once it has been calibrated with validated field observations. This tool could therefore overcome some of the challenges in quantifying the proportion of a population that is attempting reproduction, but further work is required to determine the minimum amount of time a nest needs to be alive to be detected by our method.

The age when the first reproduction attempt occurs is another important driver in the population dynamics of long-lived species (Sæther and Bakke 2000, Sergio et al. 2021), and may change in increasing populations that approach carrying capacity (Ferrer et al. 2004, Margalida et al. 2020, Katzenberger et al. 2021). Because the pre-reproductive years of long-lived animals can be difficult to observe and can be affected by emigration, our tool offers a consistent approach to quantify at what age young individuals recruit into a population and attempt reproduction. Together with reproductive success, and the use of telemetry data to estimate survival (Sergio et al. 2019, Swift et al. 2020, Buechley et al. 2021), most of the key demographic parameters that are required for understanding population dynamics can therefore be inferred from telemetry data as long as the tags do not have deleterious effects. Our tool shows that demographic parameters can be estimated for different populations using the same approach, which could facilitate opportunities to assess population dynamics at larger spatial scales without the problem of inconsistencies in estimates between local or regional studies (Mattsson et al. 2022).

In summary, NestTool facilitates the extraction of important demographic parameters from widely available tracking data for red kites in Europe. The availability of demographic information about when young birds recruit into the breeding population, and how successfully they breed, is useful to understand the population dynamics of the red kite, which may have changed in recent decades as populations have recovered (Katzenberger et al. 2019, 2021, Pfeiffer and

Schaub 2023). We encourage red kite researchers to use this tool to assess the reproductive performance of their tracked individuals, and other researchers to adopt this tool for different species.

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Transparent peer review

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Data availability statement

The code and example data to reproduce the models are available from the Zenodo Digital Repository: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13736049> (Oppel et al. 2024). The raw tracking data from Switzerland and Germany are available on www.movebank.org with MovebankID of 230545451 (Milvusmilvus_GSM_SOI), 1356790386 (Milvusmilvus_Milsar_SOI_final), and 294443150 (Red Kites (Milvus milvus) in Saxony-Anhalt).

Supporting information

The Supporting information associated with this article is available with the online version.

References

- Aebischer, A. and Scherler, P. 2021. Der Rotmilan: ein Greifvogel im Aufwind. – Haupt Verlag.
- Barraquand, F. and Benhamou, S. 2008. Animal movements in heterogeneous landscapes: identifying profitable places and homogeneous movement bouts. – *Ecology* 89: 3336–3348.
- Blas, J., Sergio, F. and Hiraldo, F. 2009. Age-related improvement in reproductive performance in a long-lived raptor: a cross-sectional and longitudinal study. – *Ecography* 32: 647–657.
- Bowgen, K. M., Dodd, S. G., Lindley, P., Burton, N. H. K. and Taylor, R. C. 2022. Curves for curlew: identifying curlew breeding status from GPS tracking data. – *Ecol. Evol.* 12: e9509.
- Bracis, C., Bildstein, K. L. and Mueller, T. 2018. Revisitation analysis uncovers spatio-temporal patterns in animal movement data. – *Ecography* 41: 1801–1811.
- Breiman, L. 2001. Random forests. – *Mach. Learn.* 45: 5–32.
- Buechley, E. R. et al. 2021. Differential survival throughout the full annual cycle of a migratory bird presents a life-history tradeoff. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 90: 1228–1238.
- Carneiro, A. P. B., Dias, M. P., Oppel, S., Pearmain, E. J., Clark, B. L., Wood, A. G., Clavelle, T. and Phillips, R. A. 2022. Integrating immersion with GPS data improves behavioural classification for wandering albatrosses and shows scavenging behind fishing vessels mirrors natural foraging. – *Anim. Conserv.* 25: 627–637.
- Catlin, D. H., Gibson, D., Hunt, K. L., Friedrich, M. J., Weithman, C. E., Karpanty, S. M. and Fraser, J. D. 2019. Direct and indirect effects of nesting density on survival and breeding propensity of an endangered shorebird. – *Ecosphere* 10: e02740.

- Chang, W., Cheng, J., Allaire, J., Sievert, C., Schloerke, B., Xie, Y., Allen, J., McPherson, J., Dipert, A. and Borges, B. 2023. shiny: web application framework for R ver. 1.9.1.9000. – <https://github.com/rstudio/shiny>.
- Cutler, D. R., Edwards, T. C., Beard, K. H., Cutler, A., Hess, K. T., Gibson, J. and Lawler, J. J. 2007. Random forests for classification in ecology. – *Ecology* 88: 2783–2792.
- Eisaguirre, J. M., Williams, P. J., Brockman, J. C., Lewis, S. B., Barger, C. P., Breed, G. A. and Booms, T. L. 2023. A hierarchical modelling framework for estimating individual- and population-level reproductive success from movement data. – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 14: 2110–2122.
- Evans, I. M., Cordero, P. J. and Parkin, D. T. 1998. Successful breeding at one year of age by red kites *Milvus milvus* in southern England. – *Ibis* 140: 53–57.
- Fauchald, P. and Tveraa, T. 2003. Using first-passage time in the analysis of area-restricted search and habitat selection. – *Ecology* 84: 282–288.
- Ferrer, M., Otorola, F. and García-Ruiz, J. M. 2004. Density-dependent age of first reproduction as a buffer affecting persistence of small populations. – *Ecol. Appl.* 14: 616–624.
- García-Macía, J., Vidal-Mateo, J., De La Puente, J., Bermejo, A., Raab, R. and Urios, V. 2022a. Seasonal differences in migration strategies of red kites (*Milvus milvus*) wintering in Spain. – *J. Ornithol.* 163: 27–36.
- García-Macía, J., Vidal-Mateo, J., de la Puente, J., Bermejo, A. and Urios, V. 2022b. Spatial ecology of the red kite (*Milvus milvus*) during the breeding period in Spain. – *Ornis Fenn.* 99: 150–162.
- Grömping, U. 2009. Variable importance assessment in regression: linear regression versus random forest. – *Am. Stat.* 63: 308–319.
- Grüneberg, C. and Karthäuser, J. 2019. Verbreitung und Bestand des Rotmilans *Milvus milvus* in Deutschland – Ergebnisse der bundesweiten Kartierung 2010–2014. – *Vogelwelt* 139: 101–116.
- Harris, M. P., Heubeck, M., Bogdanova, M. I., Newell, M. A., Wanless, S. and Daunt, F. 2020. The importance of observer effort on the accuracy of breeding success estimates in the common guillemot *Uria aalge*. – *Bird Study* 67: 93–103.
- Heiniger, N. 2020. Identifying anthropogenic feeding sites from GPS tracking data: a case study for red kites (*Milvus milvus*) in western Switzerland. – MSc thesis, Department of Geography, University of Zurich, Switzerland.
- Hinde, A. 1956. The biological significance of the territories of birds. – *Ibis* 98: 340–369.
- Hothorn, T., Müller, J., Schröder, B., Kneib, T. and Brandl, R. 2011. Decomposing environmental, spatial, and spatiotemporal components of species distributions. – *Ecol. Monogr.* 81: 329–347.
- Hötker, H., Mammen, K., Mammen, U. and Rasran, L. 2017. Red kites and wind farms – telemetry data from the core breeding range. – In: Gartman, V. and Köppel, J. (eds), *Wind energy and wildlife interactions*. Springer, pp. 3–15.
- Janitzka, S., Strobl, C. and Boulesteix, A.-L. 2013. An AUC-based permutation variable importance measure for random forests. – *BMC Bioinform.* 14: 119.
- Katzenberger, J., Gottschalk, E., Balkenhol, N. and Waltert, M. 2019. Long-term decline of juvenile survival in German red kites. – *J. Ornithol.* 160: 337–349.
- Katzenberger, J., Gottschalk, E., Balkenhol, N. and Waltert, M. 2021. Density-dependent age of first reproduction as a key factor for population dynamics: stable breeding populations mask strong floater declines in a long-lived raptor. – *Anim. Conserv.* 24: 862–875.
- Kaufmann, J. H. 1983. On the definitions and functions of dominance and territoriality. – *Biol. Rev.* 58: 1–20.
- Kays, R. et al. 2022. The Movebank system for studying global animal movement and demography. – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 13: 419–431.
- Kays, R., Crofoot, M. C., Jetz, W. and Wikelski, M. 2015. Terrestrial animal tracking as an eye on life and planet. – *Science* 348: aaa2478.
- Kidd, L. R., Sheldon, B. C., Simmonds, E. G. and Cole, E. F. 2015. Who escapes detection? Quantifying the causes and consequences of sampling biases in a long-term field study. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 84: 1520–1529.
- Klaassen, R. H. G., Hake, M., Strandberg, R., Koks, B. J., Trierweiler, C., Exo, K.-M., Bairlein, F. and Alerstam, T. 2014. When and where does mortality occur in migratory birds? Direct evidence from long-term satellite tracking of raptors. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 83: 176–184.
- Kolbe, M. and Nicolai, B. 2017. Der Rotmilan *Milvus milvus* und andere Greifvögel (Accipitridae) im nordöstlichen Harzvorland-Situation 2016. – *Ornithol. Jber Mus. Heineanum* 34: 1–22.
- Literák, I., Raab, R., Škrábal, J., Vyhnaň, S., Dostál, M., Matušík, H., Makoň, K., Maderič, B. and Spakovszky, P. 2022. Dispersal and philopatry in central European red kites *Milvus milvus*. – *J. Ornithol.* 163: 469–479.
- Longarini, A., Duriez, O., Shepard, E., Safi, K., Wikelski, M. and Scacco, M. 2023. Effect of harness design for tag attachment on the flight performance of five soaring species. – *Mov. Ecol.* 11: 39.
- López-Sepulcre, A. and Kokko, H. 2005. Territorial defense, territory size and population regulation. – *Am. Nat.* 166: 317–329.
- Maciorowski, G., Kosicki, J., Polakowski, M., Urbańska, M., Zduniak, P. and Tryjanowski, P. 2019. Autumn migration of immature red kites *Milvus milvus* from a central European population. – *Acta Ornithol.* 54: 45–50.
- Mammen, K., Mammen, U. and Resetaritz, A. 2017. Red kite. – In: Hötker, H., Krone, O. and Nehls, G. (eds), *Birds of prey and wind farms: analysis of problems and possible solutions*. Springer, pp. 13–95.
- Margalida, A., Jiménez, J., Martínez, J. M., Sesé, J. A., García-Ferré, D., Llamas, A., Razin, M., Colomer, M. À. and Arroyo, B. 2020. An assessment of population size and demographic drivers of the bearded vulture using integrated population models. – *Ecol. Monogr.* 90: e01414.
- Mateo-Tomás, P., Olea, P. P., Mínguez, E., Mateo, R. and Viñuela, J. 2020. Direct evidence of poison-driven widespread population decline in a wild vertebrate. – *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 117: 16418–16423.
- Mattsson, B. J. et al. 2022. Enhancing monitoring and transboundary collaboration for conserving migratory species under global change: the priority case of the red kite. – *J. Environ. Manage.* 317: 115345.
- Murgatroyd, M., Tate, G. and Amar, A. 2023. Using GPS tracking to monitor the breeding performance of a low-density raptor improves accuracy, and reduces long-term financial and carbon costs. – *R. Soc. Open Sci.* 10: 221447.
- Nägeli, M., Scherler, P., Witzak, S., Catitti, B., Aebischer, A., van Bergen, V., Kormann, U. and Grübler, M. U. 2022. Weather and food availability additively affect reproductive output in an expanding raptor population. – *Oecologia* 198: 125–138.

- Newton, I., Davis, P. E. and Davis, J. E. 1989. Age of first breeding, dispersal and survival of red kites *Milvus milvus* in Wales. – *Ibis* 131: 16–21.
- Nicolai, B., Mammen, U. and Kolbe, M. 2017. Long-term changes in population and habitat selection of red kite *Milvus milvus* in the region with the highest population density. – *Vogelwelt* 137: 194–197.
- Oppel, S., Beeli, U. M., Gruebler, M. U., van Bergen, V. S., Kolbe, M., Pfeiffer, T. and Scherler, P. 2024. Data from: Extracting reproductive parameters from GPS tracking data for a nesting raptor in Europe. – Zenodo Digital Repository, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13736049>.
- Orgeret, F., Gruebler, M. U., Scherler, P., Bergen, V. S. v. and Kormann, U. G. 2023. Shift in habitat selection during natal dispersal in a long-lived raptor species. – *Ecography* 2023: e06729.
- Overton, C., Casazza, M., Bretz, J., McDuie, F., Matchett, E., Mackell, D., Lorenz, A., Mott, A., Herzog, M. and Ackerman, J. 2022. Machine learned daily life history classification using low frequency tracking data and automated modelling pipelines: application to North American waterfowl. – *Mov. Ecol.* 10: 23.
- Ozsanlav-Harris, L., Griffin, L. R., Weegman, M. D., Cao, L., Hilton, G. M. and Bearhop, S. 2022. Wearable reproductive trackers: quantifying a key life history event remotely. – *Anim. Biotelem.* 10: 24.
- Panuccio, M., Mellone, U. and Agostini, N. (eds) 2021. Migration strategies of birds of prey in western Palearctic. – CRC Press.
- Peniche, G., Vaughan-Higgins, R., Carter, I., Pocknell, A., Simpson, D. and Sainsbury, A. 2011. Long-term health effects of harness-mounted radio transmitters in red kites (*Milvus milvus*) in England. – *Vet. Rec.* 169: 311–311.
- Péron, G., Walker, J., Rotella, J., Hines, J. E. and Nichols, J. D. 2014. Estimating nest abundance while accounting for time-to-event processes and imperfect detection. – *Ecology* 95: 2548–2557.
- Pfeiffer, T. 2009. Untersuchungen zur Altersstruktur von Brutvögeln beim Rotmilan *Milvus milvus*. – In: Stubbe, M. and Mammen, U. (eds), *Populationsökologie von Greifvogel- und Eulenarten* 6. Förderverein für Ökologie und Monitoring, pp. 197–210.
- Pfeiffer, T. and Meyburg, B.-U. 2015. GPS tracking of red kites (*Milvus milvus*) reveals fledgling number is negatively correlated with home range size. – *J. Ornithol.* 156: 963–975.
- Pfeiffer, T. and Meyburg, B.-U. 2022. Flight altitudes and flight activities of adult red kites (*Milvus milvus*) in the breeding area as determined by GPS telemetry. – *J. Ornithol.* 163: 867–879.
- Pfeiffer, T. and Schaub, M. 2023. Productivity drives the dynamics of a red kite source population that depends on immigration. – *J. Avian Biol.* 2023: e02984.
- Picardi, S., Smith, B. J., Boone, M. E., Frederick, P. C., Cecere, J. G., Rubolini, D., Serra, L., Pirrello, S., Borkhataria, R. R. and Basille, M. 2020. Analysis of movement recursions to detect reproductive events and estimate their fate in central place foragers. – *Mov. Ecol.* 8: 24.
- Pichler, M. and Hartig, F. 2023. Machine learning and deep learning—a review for ecologists. – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 14: 994–1016.
- Powell, R. A. and Mitchell, M. S. 2012. What is a home range? – *J. Mammal.* 93: 948–958.
- Prasad, A. M., Iverson, L. R. and Liaw, A. 2006. Newer classification and regression tree techniques: bagging and random forests for ecological prediction. – *Ecosystems* 9: 181–199.
- Riotte-Lambert, L., Benhamou, S. and Chamaillé-Jammes, S. 2016. From randomness to traplining: a framework for the study of routine movement behavior. – *Behav. Ecol.* 28: 280–287.
- Sæther, B. E. and Bakke, O. 2000. Avian life history variation and contribution of demographic traits to the population growth rate. – *Ecology* 81: 642–653.
- Scherler, P., Bergen, V. v., Catitti, B., Kormann, U., Witzczak, S., Anderegg, M., Herzog, J. S., Aebischer, A., Roth, N. and Gruebler, M. U. 2023a. Brutbiologie des Rotmilans *Milvus milvus* in den Westschweizer Voralpen. – *Ornithol. Beobachter* 120: 276–292.
- Scherler, P., Witzczak, S., Aebischer, A., van Bergen, V., Catitti, B. and Gruebler, M. U. 2023b. Determinants of departure to natal dispersal across an elevational gradient in a long-lived raptor species. – *Ecol. Evol.* 13: e9603.
- Schreven, K. H., Stolz, C., Madsen, J. and Nolet, B. A. 2021. Nesting attempts and success of Arctic-breeding geese can be derived with high precision from accelerometry and GPS-tracking. – *Anim. Biotelem.* 9: 1–13.
- Sergio, F., Tavecchia, G., Blas, J., López, L., Tanferna, A. and Hiraldo, F. 2011. Variation in age-structured vital rates of a long-lived raptor: implications for population growth. – *Basic Appl. Ecol.* 12: 107–115.
- Sergio, F., Tavecchia, G., Tanferna, A., López Jiménez, L., Blas, J., De Stephanis, R., Marchant, T. A., Kumar, N. and Hiraldo, F. 2015. No effect of satellite tagging on survival, recruitment, longevity, productivity and social dominance of a raptor, and the provisioning and condition of its offspring. – *J. Appl. Ecol.* 52: 1665–1675.
- Sergio, F., Tanferna, A., Blas, J., Blanco, G. and Hiraldo, F. 2019. Reliable methods for identifying animal deaths in GPS- and satellite-tracking data: review, testing, and calibration. – *J. Appl. Ecol.* 56: 562–572.
- Sergio, F., Tavecchia, G., Blas, J., Tanferna, A. and Hiraldo, F. 2021. Demographic modeling to fine-tune conservation targets: importance of pre-adults for the decline of an endangered raptor. – *Ecol. Appl.* 31: e2266.
- Serratos, J. et al. 2024. Tracking data highlight the importance of human-induced mortality for large migratory birds at a flyway scale. – *Biol. Conserv.* 293: 110525.
- Shamoun-Baranes, J., Bom, R., van Loon, E. E., Ens, B. J., Oosterbeek, K. and Bouten, W. 2012. From sensor data to animal behaviour: an oystercatcher example. – *PLoS One* 7: e37997.
- Spatz, T., Katzenberger, J., Friess, N., Gelpke, C., Gottschalk, E., Hormann, M., Koschkar, S., Pfeiffer, T., Stübing, S., Sudfeldt, C., Rösner, S., Schabo, D. G. and Farwig, N. 2022. Sex, landscape diversity and primary productivity shape the seasonal space use of a migratory European raptor. – *J. Avian Biol.* 2022: e02925.
- Strobl, C., Boulesteix, A.-L., Zeileis, A. and Hothorn, T. 2007. Bias in random forest variable importance measures: illustrations, sources and a solution. – *BMC Bioinformatics* 8: 25.
- Swift, R. J., Rodewald, A. D., Johnson, J. A., Andres, B. A. and Senner, N. R. 2020. Seasonal survival and reversible state effects in a long-distance migratory shorebird. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 89: 2043–2055.
- Thiebault, A., Dubroca, L., Mullers, R. H. E., Tremblay, Y. and Pistorius, P. A. 2018. ‘m2b’ package in r: deriving multiple variables from movement data to predict behavioural states with random forests. – *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 9: 1548–1555.

- van der Wal, R., Zeng, C., Heptinstall, D., Ponnampuruma, K., Mellish, C., Ben, S. and Siddharthan, A. 2015. Automated data analysis to rapidly derive and communicate ecological insights from satellite-tag data: a case study of reintroduced red kites. – *Ambio* 44: 612–623.
- Weimerskirch, H. 2018. Linking demographic processes and foraging ecology in wandering albatross – conservation implications. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 87: 945–955.
- Whitfield, D. P., Fielding, A. H., Anderson, D., Benn, S., Dennis, R., Grant, J. and Weston, E. D. 2022. Age of first territory settlement of golden eagles *Aquila chrysaetos* in a variable competitive landscape. – *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 10: 743598.
- Williams, H. J. et al. 2020. Optimizing the use of biologgers for movement ecology research. – *J. Anim. Ecol.* 89: 186–206.
- Wright, M. N. and Ziegler, A. 2017. ranger: a fast implementation of random forests for high dimensional data in C++ and R. – *J. Stat. Softw.* 77: 1–17.
- Yates, K. L. et al. 2018. Outstanding challenges in the transferability of ecological models. – *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 33: 790–802.